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NOTION OF CONDITIONAL SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Abstract. The article is based on notion of conditional sentences, the comparative analysis of the characteristics of speech in English and Uzbek. Students learn notion of sentences in English and Uzbek languages. They also find information about conditional sentences, an independent sentence, an exclamatory sentence, an interrogative sentence, a complex sentence, a mixed sentence or compound-complex sentence. The results of the article can be used in lectures and seminars on general linguistics, lexicology, comparative linguistics, linguoculturology, as well as in seminars, dissertations, textbooks, manuals.

Key words: conditional sentences, independent clause, a dependent clause, direct conditions, hypothetical conditional, future real conditional.

An analysis of industry-specific sources reveals that syntax is the study of the grammatical properties of sentences and phrases in a sentence. A speech is an elementary part of speech composed of a combination of words or a single word, expressing a relatively complete idea, formally and intonationally, and grammatically formed. Thought is formed and expressed through speech. Speech is a syntactic unit used to express thoughts, feelings, and desires to others, and is the simplest form of thought expression. Each sentence is formed according to grammatical rules, i.e. it has a certain grammatical appearance. In particular, German grammar is also a general rule that describes all forms of word association, word formation, and sentence formation. All types of phrases and sentences conform to these generalizing rules. The most important feature of a sentence is that it has a grammatical-intonational and intellectual integrity.

In linguistics, the interest of researchers in major linguistic and communicative-pragmatic units of language has been growing in recent years. In particular, simple and compound sentences from major linguistic units and their types have been in the focus of attention of many linguists. In such studies, all existing aspects of communicative units serve as the object of research, for example, their structural, semantic, cognitive, functional, pragmatic and stylistic aspects are studied with special attention by research scientists. The study of communicative units of language and their comprehensive linguistic analysis

and description has been carried out with great success not only in private linguistics but also in typological and general linguistics, but there are still a number of serious problems and issues in this field. From this point of view, the monograph of Professor of our university G.M. Hoshimov “Typology of conjunctions of languages in different systems” is devoted to a topical issue that is almost undeveloped in modern linguistics - the typology of conjunctions in languages of different systems, which is closely related to typological and general syntax theory. and a series of synonymous units in Uzbek languages [1].

Syntactically, conditional sentences consist of two clauses: the conditional clause (or if clause) which states the condition upon which the main (or result) clause depends. In Uzbek, the conditional clause is called “*shartli ergash gaplar*” and the main clause “*bosh gap*” [2]. On this point, Thomson and Martinet (1995:197) give the same opinion saying conditional sentence has two parts one of which is dependent clause and another is independent one [3].

As can be seen from the definitions given in different sources in English and Uzbek language, the structure is similar to each other. More specifically, the examples can be seen below:

If it rains, I will stay at home.

Agar yomg'ir yog'sa, men uyda qolaman.

In the first sentence, the part “If it rains” is a dependent clause (in other sources “If clause”), and the second part is called independent clause as this is the part which a speaker can use separately with a complete meaning. However, paying attention to the second sentence, here, “*Agar yomg'ir yog'sa*” is a dependent clause while the second part “*men uyda qolaman*” can be considered as an independent one.

Although a wide variety of conditional sentences can be introduced by different subordinators in both languages such as “*unless*” and “... *bo'lsa*” in English and a “*agar...masa*”, “in Uzbek, the present work is going to focus on the structure introduced by the adverbial subordinator “if” in English and “*agar*” in Uzbek [4]. Furthermore, there are other distinctions based on the syntactic role of the adverbial clause of condition within the sentence, i.e. as adjunct or as style disjunction, which Quirk has classified as direct and indirect conditions respectively [5].

According to Quirk, direct conditions, which constitute the central use of conditionals, “convey that the situation in the matrix clause is directly contingent on that of the conditional clause i.e. the truth of the proposition in the matrix clause is a consequence of the fulfillment of the condition in the conditional clause” [6].

Traugott et al. (1986:5) says that “A typical English if-conditional sentence is “If p, then q”. The if-clause (If-C) is the antecedent, in which the speaker states the condition of reasoning, and the then-clause (result-C) is the consequent in which the speaker states the outcome of inferences” [7].

At the same time, apart from the syntactic role of adverbial clause of condition within a sentence, other distinctive features can also be found here. What is meant here is that although the punctuation marks used in Uzbek and English are the same and comma “,” is used between two clauses when dependent clause comes before the independent one, in Uzbek language, the place of independent clause is fixed: it always comes after dependent one if the author wants to give the full meaning. Why this is like this is that if the places of clauses are changed in Uzbek “If” conditional sentences, they become run-on and fragments and meaningless, unfortunately. But, in English language, the rule does not apply, and the structure is free.

For example, *I will go to school if I recover till tomorrow.*

If I recover till tomorrow, I will go to school.

Agarda ertagacha sog'ayib qolsam, maktabga boraman.

Inversion in conditional sentences in Uzbek language can be applied in poetry or to emphasize something only. In other cases, only fixed structure is the best option to use so as to avoid making grammar mistakes and negatively affect the meaning of a sentence with this.

English conditional sentences can be divided into sentences of real conditions and sentences of unreal conditions. The real conditionals can be further divided into those that express some type of factual relationship and those that

present a predictive relationship. In Zhang's viewpoint, the unreal conditionals are used to express extremely unlikely or hypothetical situations and situations that are assumed to be contrary to known facts or counterfactual [8].

Based on this viewpoint, yes, it is true that in English language we have conditionals used to express unreal situations impossible to change, and this type of conditional sentences can be formed with the help of special structures. On the other hand, in Uzbek language, such structures do not nearly exist, and when one analyzes the conditionals in Uzbek, they can guess the true meaning of a sentence with the help of context. Examples can be seen below regarding this opinion:

If I won the lottery, I would buy a luxurious house. – unreal situation

If I study hard, I will go abroad to study. – real situation

Agar lotoreya yutsam, hashamatli uy sotib olaman. – unreal situation

Agar qattiq o'qisam, chet elga ta'lim olish uchun boraman. – real situation

Here, in “If” clause, the past simple and in an independent clause, modal verb with bare infinitive are used, but, in an unreal “if” clause of Uzbek language, no changes can be observed when it is compared with real “If” clause in the same language. What really matters here is the situation that the speaker and listener are.

As varied as the types of conditional sentences are, the English conditionals are further complicated by the use of back-shifting of tense. Comrie (1986) defines the backshifting of tense as “the use of a morphologically past tense with present (or future) time reference and of pluperfect with past time reference.” For example, the present tense is used to refer to the future in the if-clause of future real conditional sentences (e.g. If I have time, I will study English.); the past tense is used in the hypothetical conditional to represent improbability in the present or future (e.g. If I had time, I would study English.); and the past perfect tense is used in the counterfactual conditional to refer to impossible events that didn't happen in the past (e.g. If I had had time, I would have studied English) [9].

Perfect tenses are of great importance when it comes to forming present real, present unreal and past unreal conditional sentences in English language since they are changed into another tense in order to give the intended meaning. What is unlike here is that again, in Uzbek language, such changes are not considered as paramount one because perfect tenses are not applicable in Uzbek, again we pay attention to the contextual situation here.

If I had known you were ill, I would have visited you yesterday.

If it were not late, I would go with you.

If I earn a lot of money, I will go to travel.

In short, it can be said that in two compared languages, namely English and Uzbek, the notion of conditional sentences exists, but the way of forming is totally different: in one language, pragmatic and functional aspects are equally crucial while in another one, more attention is paid to the semantic meaning of the sentence and situation of speakers and listeners are.

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